

Effect of Nature and Concentration of Supporting Electrolyte on the Half-wave Potential and Diffusion Current. Part I

S. N. Mukherjee and Mrs. Anima Chakravarti

Influence of variation of the nature and concentration of the supporting electrolyte on the half-wave potential and diffusion current of Cd^{2+} and Zn^{2+} as reducing ions has been studied. An attempt has been made to correlate these data (specially those of the diffusion current) with viscosity, but such a correlation has been found to be not always possible. In some cases the possibility of complex formation is suggested.

In a previous communication (Mukherjee *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 77) it has been shown that there has been decrease both in the half-wave potential and in the diffusion current when the viscosity of the solution is increased gradually by addition of glycerin to the medium containing 0.1M-KCl as a supporting electrolyte and $1 \times 10^{-3}M$ of the reducible ions, Cd^{2+} and Zn^{2+} . The diffusion current was, however, found to vary linearly with the square root of D , the diffusion coefficient. This signifies that i_{d7} is expected to be constant in such cases. It is therefore concluded that mere change in the viscosity of the medium has no other significant complicating influence and obeys Ilkovic's equation in a regular manner.

In the present series of communications, it is our object to study the influence of variation of the nature and concentration of the supporting electrolyte on these two parameters and to examine whether any complicating factors arise in such cases.

EXPERIMENTAL

The present study is confined to the cases of the reducing ions Cd^{2+} and Zn^{2+} only, with the supporting electrolytes: KCl, KNO_3 , NH_4Cl , HCl. Chemicals used were all of G.R. quality of E. Merck. The instrument was found to yield $E_{1/2}$ within ± 0.005 volts and i_d within ± 0.125 μa . The drop time was about 3 secs. and the mass flow rate for mercury was 1.6 to 1.8 mg. per second. Purified nitrogen gas was passed through the solution for about 15 to 20 minutes to get rid of the dissolved oxygen. Gelatine (0.005%) was used as a suppressor in every case. $E_{1/2}$ was measured against the saturated calomel electrode.

Viscosity was measured relative to that of water by an Ostwald viscometer* at a constant temperature (accurate to $\pm 0.05^\circ$). The mean flow time of water through the capillary (based on 10 readings) was 132.95 ± 0.1 sec. Each of the viscosity readings shown here represents the mean of at least five different observations. Results are shown in Tables I and II.

*British Standard U-tube type with N.P.L. certificate.

TABLE I
 Cd²⁺ as the reducing ion.

Supporting electrolyte conc.	i_d (μ a).	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (volts).	Viscosity (η).	$i_d \eta^{\frac{1}{2}}$	i_d (μ a).	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	Viscosity (η).	$i_d \eta^{\frac{1}{2}}$.
						(volts).		
		KCl.				KNO ₃ .		
M/10	2.150	0.612	1.004	2.154	..	..	0.998	..
M/2	2.175	0.632	1.017	2.104	1.500	0.595	0.980	1.485
M	2.200	0.647	1.019	2.220	1.500	0.595	0.974	1.490
2M	2.225	0.660	1.073	2.305	1.500	0.595	0.958	1.468
		NH ₄ Cl.				HCl.		
M/10	..	..	1.000	..	3.000	0.640	1.009	3.013
M/2	1.750	0.642	0.986	1.740	3.000	0.675	1.063	3.092
M	1.900	0.670	0.985	1.888	3.000	0.720	1.112	3.163
2M	1.750	0.687	0.980	1.732	3.000	0.757	1.214	3.321

 TABLE II
 Zn²⁺ as the reducing ion.

Supporting electrolyte conc.	i_d (μ a).	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (volts).	Viscosity (η).	$i_d \eta^{\frac{1}{2}}$.	i_d (μ a).	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	Viscosity (η).	i_d (η) ^{1/2} .
						(volts).		
		KCl				KNO ₃		
M/10	1.000	1.100	1.002	1.000	1.450	1.080	0.993	1.445
M/2	1.050	1.065	0.984	1.041	1.475	1.110	0.984	1.464
M	1.650	1.0425	0.981	1.634	1.500	1.110	0.986	1.474
2M	1.950	1.040	0.972	1.923	1.525	1.062	0.982	1.495
		NH ₄ Cl.						
M/10	1.700	1.120	0.993	1.694				
M/2	1.700	1.170	0.990	1.698				
M	1.700	1.115	0.993	1.694				
2M	1.650	1.130	0.994	1.641				

It will be evident from the columns of viscosity that in presence of Cd²⁺ ions (of the concentration of the order of 10⁻⁴ M) viscosities of KCl and HCl solutions slightly increase with increasing concentration, whereas those with KNO₃ and NH₄Cl exhibit a slight diminution. In the case of Zn²⁺ ion (present in the same concentration) the salts, KCl and KNO₃, uniformly show slight diminution of relative viscosity with increasing concentrations of the supporting electrolytes. Such a behaviour is not quite unexpected, as studied by Jones and Dole (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 2950) as well as by Joy and Wolfenden (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1932, 134A, 424) who related viscosity with concentration from the point of view of the Debye-Hückel theory and obtained a complicated relationship (vide Gurney, "Ionic Processes in Solution", McGraw Hill Book Co. Inc., 1953, p. 160).

The diffusion current i_d increases with increasing KCl concentration in the case of Cd²⁺ and Zn²⁺ ions, whereas in both the cases it remains constant in the cases of KNO₃ and NH₄Cl. With HCl, however, the case of Cd²⁺ could only be studied; i_d was found to remain constant in spite of the change in viscosity.

The half-wave potential shows a slight increase with concentration of the supporting electrolytes KCl, NH₄Cl, and HCl in the case of Cd²⁺. With KNO₃ and Cd²⁺ ion, $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ remains almost at a constant value. In the case of Zn²⁺ ion, all the three electrolytes, KCl, KNO₃, and NH₄Cl, showed almost constant $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ at all concentrations.

Coming back again to the case of Cd²⁺ and KCl, we find that with increasing concentration of KCl both i_d and η increase. $i_d \eta^{\frac{1}{2}}$ also shows a regular increase. This appears to be

peculiar because i_d should diminish with viscosity. If the former were dependent on viscosity alone, as reported earlier (*loc cit.*), $i_{d7\frac{1}{2}}$ should remain constant. But a systematic increase of the product definitely shows that there is some other factors appearing which may be responsible for the increase in i_d beyond proportions. What this other factor may be, is difficult to anticipate off hand. From the literature (Kolthoff and Lingane, "Polarography", Vol. I, 2nd ed., 1952, p. 96) we find that in presence of Cl^- ions both Cd^{2+} and Zn^{2+} have tendencies to form complexes CdCl^+ and ZnCl^+ which being monovalent will be expected to have a high diffusion coefficient according to the equation in which the valency Z appears in the denominator:

$$D^\circ = 2.67 \times 10^{-7} \frac{\lambda^\circ}{Z} \text{ (cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1} \text{ at } 25^\circ\text{)}$$

The case of Zn^{2+} and KCl appears to have a more marked but similar effect. The same cause may also be responsible in this case too. The case of Cd^{2+} and HCl is similar probably due to the same reason.

Using KNO_3 as the supporting electrolyte, there is hardly any change in the product $i_{d7\frac{1}{2}}$ with Cd^{2+} ion. There appears to be a slight decrease at a concentration of $2M$ - KNO_3 which may be due to the effect of viscosity being quite less at this high concentration. In the case of Zn^{2+} and KNO_3 , the product, $i_{d7\frac{1}{2}}$, shows slight increase with increasing concentration, similar to Zn^{2+} and KCl , but the effect is less marked in this case. What this is due to, is not very clear. It may be that Zn^{2+} has a tendency to form a complex with NO_3^- ion also even at such an ionic strength as has been suggested in the case of Cd^{2+} by Meites ("Polarographic Techniques", Interscience Publishers, 1955, p. 124).

In presence of NH_4Cl and Cd^{2+} , the values of i_d are slightly less than those with KCl but greater than those in KNO_3 and they show little variation with concentration. The half-wave potentials of Cd^{2+} in KCl and NH_4Cl are almost of the same order, but concentrations of NH_4Cl have very little influence on $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$. $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ values in presence of KNO_3 are decidedly the lowest, but those with HCl show higher values. Viscosity (η) appears to show no change with concentration of NH_4Cl and therefore the product $i_{d7\frac{1}{2}}$ remains almost constant as expected. With Zn^{2+} and NH_4Cl , i_d shows practically no change unlike the case of KCl or KNO_3 . $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ also remains practically constant in this case and product $i_{d7\frac{1}{2}}$ shows the constant expected values.

It is to be noted in this connection that with Cd^{2+} in presence of KCl and HCl , there a possibility of complex formation of Cd^{2+} and Cl^- ions and so the peculiar behaviour, as mentioned above, appears with NH_4Cl also. The case shows, however, no abnormality but always yields a normal behaviour. Whether this is due to the absence of the complex formation or due to any effect of the NH_4^+ ion cannot, however, be ascertained without further investigation. Kolthoff and Lingane (*loc cit.*, p. 97) refers to the formation of ammonia complex with both Cd^{2+} and Zn^{2+} in an ammoniacal medium of NH_4Cl . The present case, however, differs from that mentioned by Kolthoff and Lingane. Whether complex formation of Cd^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions occurs simultaneously with NH_4^+ and Cl^- ions and how far such a possibility can explain this fact are not yet understood.

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